

THE TWOSPOTTED SPIDER MITE'S BIOLOGY AND LIFE TABLE CHARACTERISTICS AS THEY RELATE TO APPLE CULTIVAR THE URTICA TETRANYCHUS

¹Rano Muminova Dalabaevna, ²Ablazova Moxichexra

¹Candidate of agricultural sciences, docent

²Assistant of the Department of Plant Protection, Tashkent State Agrarian University,
Tashkent-100140, University str., 2, Uzbekistan.

Email: muminova.rano@tdau.uz

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Abstract. *Tetranychus urticae* Koch is a significant global pest that harms various plants, including fruit trees, vegetables, and flowers. Acaricides are often used to manage *T. urticae* in apple orchards, but the presence of resistant populations limits the consequences. The short life cycle, strong reproductive capacity, and haplo-diploid parthenogenesis make *T. urticae* a relatively high risk of developing pesticide resistance. The shelf life of acaricides is getting shorter, and monitoring local population resistance is crucial for efficient management. Aerial dispersal is a crucial factor in population dynamics, and the method of dissemination depends on the environment. Aerial dispersal in field populations is sped up by deteriorating environmental conditions, increased predator density, and the use of an acaricide. Migration rates and mean dispersal distances related to both aerial and crawling processes may change over time.

Keywords: *tetranychus*, *egg*, *spider mites*, *twospotted*, *biology*, *populations*, *parthenogenesis*

Introduction. Apples are severely harmed by *Tetranychus urticae* Koch around the world. Acaricides are frequently used by farmers to manage *T. urticae* in apple orchards. However, the presence of resistant populations limits the consequences. Due to its short life cycle, strong reproductive capacity, and haplo-diploid parthenogenesis, *T. urticae* has a relatively high risk of developing pesticide resistance. There are several reports on the emergence of *T. urticae* strains that are resistant to acaricides as well as the failure of these compounds to control *T. urticae*. The shelf life of acaricides is getting shorter. The monitoring of local population resistance is the first step in the efficient management of *T. urticae*. To limit the evolution of resistance in *T. urticae* and postpone the dissemination of resistant populations, a deeper comprehension of resistance development is needed.

The capability of herbivorous arthropods to disperse across accessible host plants is a crucial factor in population dynamics. The wingless spider mites typically rely on crawling for their dispersal, unlike many herbivorous arthropods that have winged adult stages that may fly great distances in search of appropriate host plants. Shorter-scale movements required by crawling dispersal are mostly tailored to the location of food and for breeding colony growth into regions with the same plant that are not already afflicted. Spider mites may nevertheless fly and travel enormous distances in the wind in addition to crawling.

In large-scale prey-predator systems, aerial dispersal may have an impact on population dynamics and speed up migration to uninfested crops. Additionally linked to the transmission of the acaricide resistant genes is aerial dispersal. A given mite's method of dissemination will generally depend on its environment. The proportion of individuals that engage in aerial dispersion behavior in laboratory settings rises with habitat degradation, such as an increase in

population density or a decline in host quality. Aerial dispersal in field populations was sped up by deteriorating environmental circumstances, an increase in predator density, and the use of an acaricide. As a result, it is anticipated that migration rates and mean dispersal distances related to both aerial and crawling processes may change over time.

Tetranychus urticae Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae), a two-spotted spider mite, is a significant global species that harms a wide range of plants, including fruit trees, vegetables, and flowers. The two-spotted spider mite is a serious pest in greenhouses, agriculture fields, and fruit orchards because it has developed resistance to several types of acaricides. In order to effectively control mite populations, it may be beneficial to have a better knowledge of dispersion. This will allow for more accurate population dynamics estimations and reduce the danger of acaricide resistance genes propagating.

The following phenological occurrences are frequently seen in Korean apple orchards where *Tetranychus urticae* creates a severe problem, as they are in other nations. *T. urticae* hibernate as orange-colored female adults, often beneath the ground cover and under the tough bark scales on the tree trunk bases. The overwintering females become active, relocate to ground weeds, and start feeding in the spring as the temperature warms up. Later in the growth season, *T. urticae* that have grown on weeds go into trees. When ground cover changes owing to herbicide spraying, its spread is sped up.

Picture 1. Orchard block 3, 2002: mean ($\pm$ SE) counts of *T. urticae* in laneway quadrats (a), upward and downward crawling *T. urticae* (b) and phytoseiids (c) caught on sticky bands, and number of *T. urticae*, *P. ulmi* and phytoseiids per leaf in the outer canopy of apple trees (d). Arrow indicates date of application of the acaricide, pyridaben (Hardman J. M. 2007)

Up until the 1990s, the only significant, pervasive mite pest in apple orchards in Nova Scotia, Canada, was the European red mite *Panonychus ulmi* (Koch). In the aftermath of the use

of pyrethroids to control the winter moth *Operophtera brumata* or fruit-stinging mirids like the tarnished plant bug *Lygus lineolaris*, there were severe outbreaks that were related to the suppression of the phytoseiid mite *Typhlodromus pyri* Scheuten. An organophosphate/pyrethroid resistant strain of *T. pyri* was introduced from New Zealand to address this issue. Releases of *T. pyri* via summer-pruned branches in commercial orchards started in 1993 after fruitful tests in research orchards. The Maritime Provinces of Canada had a large population of pyrethroid-resistant *T. pyri* by the late 1990s, and effective biological control was frequently achieved within 1-3 years following the release of a predator.

Tetranychus urticae Koch, a two-spotted spider mite that was formerly of little consequence, turned into a significant nuisance in the late 1990s amid a run of hot, dry summers. Even in orchards where *T. pyri* was present and acaricides were used, *T. urticae* populations occasionally surpassed the economic threshold. Due to its low to moderate rates of eating and reproduction as a type 3 generalist predator, *T. pyri* has a limited capacity to control spider mites during a single season and occasionally fails to control *T. urticae* in orchards. Hardman et al. (2005, 2006) undertook a 2-year research in 12–15 commercial apple orchards to investigate the causes of *T. urticae* outbreaks.

They discovered, among other things, that: (1) *T. urticae* densities in tree canopies were correlated with the number of *T. urticae* crawling up tree trunks; (2) *T. pyri* inhibited *T. urticae* population growth in trees; (3) midsummer heat and drought promoted *T. urticae* immigration into trees and population growth in the tree canopy; and (4) the only canopy pesticides associated with higher rates of *T. urticae* immigration and population growth

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